

CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR 6G

D4.3 – CONFIDENTIAL ORCHESTRATION

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
AI	<i>Artificial Intelligence</i>
CCA	<i>Confidential Compute Architecture – from ARM</i>
CNI	<i>Container Network Interface</i>
CNN	<i>Convolutional Neural Network</i>
CoCo	<i>Confidential Container – particularly in a reference to the open-source project</i>
CSV	<i>China Security Virtualization - a security virtualization technology developed by HYGON, implemented with Chinese cryptographic algorithms</i>
CVM	<i>Confidential Virtual Machine</i>
DLT	<i>Distributed Ledger Technology</i>
FHE	<i>Fully Homomorphic Encryption</i>
FL	<i>Federated Learning</i>
FPGA	<i>Field-Programmable Gate Array</i>
iDLG	<i>Improved Gradient Leakage attack</i>
K8s	<i>Kubernetes</i>
KBS	<i>Key Broker Service – from the CoCo Trustee project</i>
ML	<i>Machine Learning</i>
OP-TEE	<i>Open Portable Trusted Execution Environment</i>
PoC	<i>Proof of Concept</i>
RATS	<i>Remote Attestation Procedures</i>
REE	<i>Rich Execution Environment</i>
SEV	<i>Secure Encrypted Virtualization – from AMD</i>
SGX	<i>Software Guard Extension – from Intel</i>
SMPC	<i>Secure Multi-Party Computation</i>
TCB	<i>Trusted Computing Base</i>
TDX	<i>Trust Domain Extension – from Intel</i>
TEE	<i>Trusted Execution Environment</i>
TLS	<i>Transmission Layer Security</i>
VM	<i>Virtual Machine</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes work done in Task 4.3 of the CONFIDENTIAL6G (C6G) project. The report explores the drivers and technologies for confidential orchestration – i.e., for automating deployment and configuration of security critical applications, services, and AI solutions - in the 6G landscape. The report describes enablers and our proof-of-concepts for managing confidential workflows to edge-cloud-IoT infrastructure that cannot be fully trusted by the 6G operators.

We contribute by enabling and verifying feasibility of confidential container technology implementations at the cloud-edge-IoT continuum. Further, we provide a structured review and analysis of the motives, requirements, threats, and technologies towards confidential orchestration approaches. Key innovations of the work include:

- Proposing a consolidated architecture that considers confidential orchestration over diverse platforms in heterogeneous computing infrastructure and addresses role of data sharing and remote attestation approaches in increasing trust towards diverse and distributed applications.
- Exploring and mitigating the energy and computational costs of confidential containers: measuring overhead of confidential containers on ARM-based edge devices and proposing an optimization approach (scheduling which is driven by sustainability and security).
- Improving the security of confidential orchestration: studying and mitigating the side-channel threats against confidential containers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Security is a vital enabler of orchestration. Confidential computing concepts studied in the C6G project can solve many cyber threats related to the 6G infrastructure and thus enable us to deploy code and data to any location, even if the code and data are security-sensitive and the infrastructure is not under the operator's control or fully trusted.

This task addresses the secure orchestration of confidential algorithms, software, and datasets that originate from different stakeholders and are distributed across the network using the data-sharing platform defined in Task T4.2. The orchestration framework must enable the secure deployment and coordination of these components while operating under strict security principles, including least-privilege execution, hardware-based Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs), and defined protocols for remote attestation.

Studies are also needed to understand the requirements stemming from the 6G use cases and technologies and to define architecture and enablers to facilitate the adaptation of security hardware and advanced cryptographic techniques in future networks.

Software and service orchestration in the context of 6G networks aims to make the following advances:

- Increase efficiency and scalability of services, which are offered through 6G networks.
- Improve reliability, resilience, and availability as systems' responses to failures can be automated and rapidly executed.
- Simplify management and increase automation to minimize end-user labour and to enable functionality which would be unfeasible without automation. Simplification is essential in the mobile network evolution that has been characterized by increasing complexity (which follows, e.g., from integration of various technologies, ambitious performance objectives, and introduction of new services while maintaining compatibility).
- Optimize used resources and thus minimize investments and operational costs. This will help to make 6G systems more environmentally friendly and economically sustainable.

- Enable portability and platform agnosticity to achieve seamless movability of services. This will facilitate reliability and resiliency (by quickly responding to failures) and cost-efficiency (by removing vendor lock-ins).

The confidential computing paradigm, on the other hand, aims to increase the security and privacy level of networks and enable operators and end-users to deploy services and data into infrastructure that is outsourced or potentially compromised by an attacker. This report focuses on confidential computing approaches that leverage security hardware, i.e., trusted execution environments (TEEs), and explores their intersection with orchestration. Therefore, we study orchestration technologies supporting TEEs, including Confidential Containers and Kubernetes. However, we will also briefly cover other technological alternatives for confidentiality.

This report is organized as follows: In Section 2, we provide background information to help the reader understand orchestration-related concepts and technologies, as well as the security gaps addressed by confidential computing technologies. Section 3 examines the requirements and threats in the 6G context more closely. Section 4 describes architectural enablers for confidential orchestration, analysing key building blocks and our proposals. Our technology experiments and proof-of-concepts are detailed in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 concludes the work by summarizing the main results and highlighting future research directions.

2 BACKGROUND ON ORCHESTRATION

This section studies and surveys orchestration-related background. In the following subsections, we will first highlight technologies related to non-confidential orchestration. Then, we will examine traditional approaches for securing orchestration. Finally, we will provide background information on confidentiality approaches for orchestration.

2.1 ORCHESTRATION

Orchestration systems are a cornerstone of infrastructure for cloud computing as well as for 5G/6G networks. Software orchestration refers to the automated coordination, configuration, and management of interconnected computer systems, applications, services, data pipelines, and AI models. Unlike simple automation, which executes tasks independently, orchestration involves intelligent decision-making to manage dependencies, enforce execution order, and maintain the consistency and health of services across a distributed architecture. It coordinates interactions between different systems and services by scaling applications up or down, monitoring, and managing the order and timing of operations.

2.1.1 VIRTUALIZATION AND CONTAINERIZATION

Virtualization and containerization are essential enablers in the orchestration of 6G services. Virtualization creates an abstraction layer between the physical hardware and the software, making it easy to provision and deploy new virtual machines (VMs). Virtualization facilitates the scaling of resources allocated for different applications, allowing operators to quickly respond to changing business needs and recover from disasters.

Containerization is a form of operating system virtualization that allows operators to run an application and its dependencies in isolated user spaces. Containers share the host operating system's kernel, making them much lighter (with fast start-up times and the use of fewer resources) than VMs.

Containers are essential building blocks for flexible and dynamic deployment and scaling of networked services. They provide portability by containing the application along with all its dependencies, including libraries and configuration files, making it easy to move containers between different environments. Containers are inherently designed for portability and rapid deployment, but

managing large numbers of containers manually would be very complex. Consequently, orchestration tools and systems have been proposed for their management.

2.1.2 ORCHESTRATION SYSTEMS

Software orchestration systems manage the complexities of distributed 6G applications. [71] Orchestration platforms automate the deployment, scaling, and operational management of workloads, which can range from containerized applications to virtual machines and legacy software.

Kubernetes, originating from Google and maintained by the Cloud Native Computing Foundation [72], has emerged as the most prominent system in the container orchestration landscape. Kubernetes provides an extensive feature set and a broad ecosystem, making it a popular choice for many software deployment cases. However, there are also other platforms for orchestration with distinct characteristics and capabilities.

For instance:

- Red Hat OpenShift [20] is a hybrid cloud application orchestration system built upon the foundation of Kubernetes.
- HashiCorp Nomad [21] presents itself as a compact and versatile orchestrator capable of supporting a wide array of workload types, extending beyond containers to include virtual machines, Java applications, and Windows services, all within a unified platform.
- Docker Swarm [22] is Docker's native clustering and orchestration tool, seamlessly integrated into the Docker Engine. It offers a straightforward approach to managing Docker containers across multiple hosts, emphasizing ease of use and quick setup.
- Amazon Elastic Container Service (ECS) [23] is a highly scalable and performant container orchestration service provided by Amazon Web Services (AWS).
- Azure Container Instances (ACI) [24] is Microsoft Azure's serverless container runtime that provides a simplified way to run containers without the complexities of orchestration.
- Google Cloud Run [25] is a serverless platform on Google Cloud that allows users to run stateless containers that automatically scale based on incoming requests. It abstracts away most of the operational burden, including infrastructure management, cluster creation, and scaling tasks.

- Apache Mesos [26] is a powerful cluster management tool that excels at resource isolation and sharing across distributed applications and frameworks.
- Rancher [27] is a user-friendly platform designed to simplify the management of Kubernetes clusters across various environments.
- Lightweight Kubernetes distributions like K3s [28], k0s [29], and MicroK8s [30] provide simplified Kubernetes implementations suitable for edge computing, IoT, or development environments.

2.1.3 KUBERNETES OVERVIEW

Kubernetes (K8s) [40] is a prominent container orchestration system. It is an open-source system designed to automate the deployment, scaling, and management of containerized applications. Kubernetes provides scalability by enabling dynamic reallocation of resources, reliability by automatically restarting failed containers, portability by enabling applications to run consistently in different environments, and efficiency by optimizing resource utilization.

Figure 1. Kubernetes architecture (adapted from [9]) with confidential containers highlighted

Key concepts of Kubernetes include:

- Pod – smallest deployable unit of computing, one or more containers sharing storage and network resources
- Node – physical or virtual machine that runs containers
- Cluster – group of nodes working together
- Namespaces – mean to organize resources within cluster

- Workload – application or service running on Kubernetes cluster. Kubernetes provides few workloads for simplifying management of user's containers and thus easing scaling, availability assurance, and self-healing.

The Kubernetes architecture is modular and consists of the control and the data plane, which are illustrated in Figure 1.

The control plane manages the state of cluster and makes decisions about how applications should run. The control plane consists of the following components:

- ***kube-apiserver*** is a front-end that enables interactions with the cluster by exposing the Kubernetes API and validating and processing API requests.
- ***etcd*** stores cluster data, including configurations, states, and metadata.
- ***kube-scheduler*** assigns pods onto worker nodes by considering resource requirements, constraints, and other factors to determine the best node for each pod.
- ***kube-controller-manager*** runs various controller processes that regulate the state of the cluster.
- ***cloud-controller-manager*** is an optional component that integrates Kubernetes with cloud provider APIs and handles cloud-specific functions, such as managing load balancers and storage volumes. The control plane components typically run on dedicated machines, i.e., on control plane nodes or master nodes.

The data plane consists of the worker nodes where applications run. Key components of the data plane include:

- ***kubelet*** which communicates with the control plane and ensures that containers are running as specified in the pod definitions.
- ***kube-proxy*** network rules that allow network communication to pods within or from outside of the cluster.
- ***Container runtime*** is software responsible for running containers. Examples of container runtimes or platforms for container runtimes include Docker, containerd, and CRI-O.

2.2 ORCHESTRATION AND CYBERSECURITY

This subsection surveys security solutions and research related to orchestration. It aims to provide high-level view to the current state in all security areas while the next subsection focuses on the related work on confidential computing and orchestration.

2.2.1 KUBERNETES SECURITY

Kubernetes has several built-in security features (not related to confidential computing) that can be used to authorize and control its use [15]. To secure the network layer, Kubernetes provides Network Policies [16], a mechanism to control the network traffic between pods, allowing for the implementation of network segmentation and isolation. Network plugins, often based on the Container Network Interface (CNI), are used to implement the underlying network fabric and enforce these policies.

There are also several third-party security tools for container vulnerability scanning and management, runtime security monitoring and posture management, and assuring authenticity of containers.

Table 1. Conventional security mechanisms for Kubernetes

Category	Security features/tools	Description
Kubernetes built-in security	Role-based access controls	Defining user and group policies and enforcing who can access Kubernetes resources
	Network policies	Limiting communication between pods and external services
	Pod Security Admission	Limiting who can use pods and how much. Replacing Pod Security Policies.
	Kubernetes Secrets	Storing sensitive information
3 rd party vulnerability management	Clair	Open-source project for the static analysis of vulnerabilities in application containers
	Trivy	Open-source tool for scanning container images for vulnerabilities
	Anchore	Platform providing vulnerability scanning and image signing
	Aqua Security	Platform integrating several security functions, including vulnerability scanning, access control, runtime protection, auditing, and security posture (integrity & compliance) management.
3 rd party runtime security	Falco	Open-source anomaly and attack detection within Kubernetes clusters
	Sysdig Secure	commercial threat detection and response platform
	KubeSec	An open-source tool for assessing the security posture of Kubernetes configurations.
Container integrity	Notary	Solution for signing container images, mitigates supply chain risks
	Connosseur	Kubernetes admission controller. Intercepts requests to Kubernetes API server to verify container images before they are deployed or updated.

2.2.2 EUROPEAN RESEARCH ON SECURITY IN 6G ORCHESTRATION

The security of orchestration and utilization of trusted computing technologies and privacy enhancing cryptography is an active research topic. For instance, several ongoing European 6G-IA/SNS projects [2] are addressing confidential orchestrations (including remote attested deployment and configuration) and introducing new functions:

- DESIRE-6G is developing mutual attestation approach where integrity records are protected with blockchain. They also aim to eliminate infrastructure constraints from deployments with platform agnostic-attestation. Similar to C6G, their focus is similarly strongly on confidential (trusted) computing technologies.
- iTrust6G combines remote attestation with supply chain vulnerability and AI-based behavioural analysis for orchestration of security
- SAFE-6G works in the configuration realm and proposes use of AI to transforming user-originated intents into system configurations that align with trustworthiness levels.
- RIGOUROUS addresses resource management over Cloud-edge-IoT-continuum. They introduce DevSecOps approach with AI-driven security orchestration and intent-based security management. Their orchestration framework aims to addresses network complexity and heterogeneity with decentralized management and they have introduced multi-cluster resource manager to optimize resource allocations across distributed clusters. AI-driven decision engine and threat risk assessor provide contextual insights to prioritize risks and guide orchestration.
- PRIVATEER work on privacy related question in decentralization of the 6G architecture and data analytics. Privacy-awareness of orchestration is emphasized to maintain trust in heterogeneous networks. They work also on security orchestration (SOAR), evaluation of end-to-end level of trust based on integrity, confidentiality, and resilience, as well as protection of cyber threat intelligence using FL and FHE.
- ACROSS works on security and trust services, including continuous remote attestation, dynamic service management. They automate migration (or orchestration) of containers from compromised to healthy node to ensure resilience.
- 6G-BRICKS works on software defined perimeters (SDP) and zero trust concept. They contribute by increasing scalability of security management

with policy and intent-based configuration and with integration of SDP with service security orchestrators.

Common strategic recommendations for security and privacy from ongoing SNS-projects [2] include enhancing decentralization to avoid single points of failure, privacy-preserving analytics to support orchestration, AI-driven automation, real-time trust measurements (in all layers and holistically), decentralized verification, integration of architectures for heterogeneous platforms, and cross-domain collaboration. These principles may also be applicable for confidential orchestration.

2.3 CONFIDENTIAL ORCHESTRATION

Confidential orchestration refers to the automated deployment and configuration of applications, functions, and data to different computing platforms for execution in a manner that keeps the application isolated and confidential from the platform provider. Confidential orchestration is an extension of the software orchestration concept, extending it to security and confidentiality-protected applications that are safeguarded using trusted hardware platforms or privacy-enhancing cryptography (enabling technologies addressed more closely in other C6G deliverables).

2.3.1 THE CONFIDENTIAL CONTAINER PROJECT

The Confidential Containers (CoCo) project [4][5] enhances the security of containerized applications by leveraging TEEs. It is an open-source project under the Cloud Native Computing Foundation and it has been designed to integrate seamlessly with cloud-native technologies, particularly Kubernetes. CoCo aims to standardize confidential computing at the pod level, supporting multiple TEEs and hardware platforms. CoCo enables containers to run within TEEs, effectively creating a secure enclave for the containerized application [6]. TEEs provide a hardware-backed secure and isolated environment within a processor, ensuring that code and data loaded inside are protected (with respect to confidentiality and integrity) from the other software and applications in the platform. TEEs are supported by major CPU vendors like Intel (with SGX and TDX), AMD (with SEV-SNP) and ARM (with TrustZone).

2.3.2 ORCHESTRATION AND ADVANCED CRYPTOGRAPHY

In addition to studying TEE-based confidential computations, the C6G project also addresses cryptographic computations based on Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) and Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC). FHE and SMPC provide

alternative approaches to secure applications and functions which are deployed to remote untrustworthy locations.

FHE allows computations to be performed on encrypted data without the need for decryption, offering a potential solution to address specific security concerns inherent in containerized and orchestrated environments. By enabling data to remain protected even during processing, FHE presents a paradigm shift in data security, extending beyond encryption at rest and in transit to include encryption in use. Architecturally, FHE involves encrypting data before it is deployed in containers. Computations on this encrypted data are then performed within the containers, with the results remaining encrypted until they are retrieved and decrypted by an authorized entity.[13][14]

Potential use cases of FHE in the context of containers also include scanning and verification. Vulnerability scanning of container images typically requires access to the unencrypted image layers. By leveraging FHE, it may become possible to perform these scans on encrypted container images without decrypting them.[18]

The widespread implementation of FHE for securing containers and software orchestration currently faces several significant limitations, primarily related to performance overhead and practical challenges. Another practical challenge lies in the complexity of key generation, management, and distribution in FHE systems. To minimize computational overhead, Enkrypt AI has presented a concept for coupling FHE with CoCo to secure critical AI workflows [19]. They applied a risk-based approach to determine which parts of the ML model should be encrypted and what can be run inside confidential containers.

2.3.3 OTHER HARDWARE-BASED CONFIDENTIAL ORCHESTRATION APPROACHES

In addition to the CoCo project, there are several alternative hardware-leveraging approaches for orchestrating confidential applications. For instance, Parma [11][12] is a Microsoft-originated technology for deploying confidential containers on the Azure cloud. Parma focuses on providing strong security for containerized applications by using virtual machine-level isolation offered by AMD SEV-SNP. Extensible Orchestration and Protection Framework (eOPF) [3] aims to provide an extensible framework for confidential cloud computing by leveraging Intel SGX enclaves. eOPF is beneficial for enhancing the security of existing applications already leveraging SGX enclaves, especially in scenarios where mitigating side-channel attacks is a critical requirement. Confidential orchestration approaches also include FPGA application deployment and configuration. For instance, Xiphera

has developed [1] an FPGA based TEE implementation for hosting critical (AI) applications. FPGA applications were deployed as encrypted packages and the trusted base included TLS server for configuring the application.

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3 REQUIREMENTS FOR CONFIDENTIAL ORCHESTRATION IN THE 6G NETWORKS

The fundamental objective of bringing confidentiality to orchestration is to increase the security level of software in 6G networks by reducing the threat landscape. Essentially, we aim to facilitate the adoption of a new trust model where service providers and users do not need to trust the service platform providers or platform operators. This is achieved by keeping orchestrated applications isolated from the platform service provider, i.e., preventing the platform provider from reading or modifying orchestrated code or data, while at the same time enabling automated deployment and configurations to third-party infrastructure.

This section studies more closely the requirements we aim to address. What is missing from regular orchestration systems that motivate the adoption of the confidential computing paradigm? What are the requirements for confidential orchestration systems, focusing particularly on the needs in 6G? What are the gaps and threats in existing technologies? We then highlight the principle of least privilege and zero-trust as guiding requirement for the architecture defined in the following section.

3.1 ORCHESTRATION CHALLENGES FROM THE 6G USE CASES

Telecommunication network architecture and emerging 6G use cases introduce specific challenges for confidential orchestration. 6G networks are expected to be significantly more complex and dynamic than their predecessors. Further, they are envisioned to support a plethora of novel applications ranging from holographic communications and digital twins to autonomous systems and enhanced industrial automation. The scale and dynamism of 6G as well as heterogeneity of components and applications demands automation and orchestration systems capable of autonomous decision-making and proactive adaptation.

6G use cases and their impact on orchestration requirements include, e.g.:

- Enhanced mobile broadband requires orchestration to efficiently manage bandwidth requirements and ensure seamless handovers. This may imply dynamic offloading of compute and AI task to the edge to support demanding applications and heterogeneous (space, aerial, terrestrial) networks. Availability of network services requires that the edge devices are

operational, these services may also handle privacy related information revealing, e.g., user movements and locations.

- Ultra-reliable low latency communications, require seamless coverage and self-healing capabilities, which means offloading of services close to users as well as rapid fallback orchestrations. Orchestration solutions provide resilience also in a case of cyberattacks impacting computing capabilities in specific locations.
- Massive machine type communications require capabilities to orchestrate services in scalable and zero-touch management manner.
- Autonomous vehicles require orchestration where services are tightly coordinated and able to follow the vehicles. Services offloaded to edge can perform low-latency computing-intensive tasks close to vehicles. Orchestrated services are highly integrity and availability critical. Orchestration can extend from edge to user vehicles.
- Smart cities use case require orchestration of code supporting heterogeneous devices and real-time analytics over privacy (confidentiality) critical data.
- Industrial application requires orchestration of automation and services which are reliability critical and often contain business secrets. Consequently, orchestration platform must provide strong integrity and often confidentiality guarantees. Orchestration can extend from edge to industrial IoT devices.
- Extended reality applications require ultra-low high-bandwidth services and will therefore benefit from edge. Some applications, like healthcare, may be very privacy/confidentiality critical, while some, like remote control of unmanned vehicles, is very integrity and availability critical.

Consequently, the challenges that the orchestration system should be able to manage include:

- **Rapid deployment** – deployment time must be short particularly in use cases where user is moving. Sometimes deployment cannot be anticipated in advance (e.g. in error recovery case) which require that also unscheduled deployments must be rapid.
- **Complexity** – 6G networks are highly complex due to various applications, technologies, devices and users that all must be supported. Further complexity arises from the cooperation between different operators – private and public – to create seamless end-to-end services. Complex configuration

of orchestration can cause additional burden for human administrators and exposes networks for security vulnerabilities.

- **Scalability** - Centralized orchestration models may not be scalability for massive and dynamic deployments. Further, Kubernetes is designed for horizontal scaling of computation nodes, may face limitations in the context of 6G infrastructure where nodes are often tied to physical devices.
- **Resilience and standalone functionality** – Some use cases imply architectures where confidential payload run devices that are sometimes offline and not connected to remote security orchestrator or attester. Architectures that rely on the presence of centralized security services are therefore more vulnerable for disruptions.
- **Interoperability with different 6G infrastructure providers** – One goal of 6G orchestration is to enable flexible use of different infrastructure and architecture alternatives when deploying services and applications. The new trust model or the adaptation of confidential computing paradigm should not significantly impact the choice of infrastructure. Confidential orchestration can be based on different technologies and platforms. Orchestration to trusted HW-based platforms requires the TEE environment (such as AMD SEV, Intel SGX, and ARM TrustZone).
- Confidential software should be seamlessly usable on different confidential computing platforms without making modifications, e.g., to container images. Virtualization, and e.g. Confidential Containers, is one approach to achieve this platform agnosticity. Confidential applications should also be deployable to platforms with different computational capabilities. Confidential workloads should be distributable to the edge-cloud continuum. Therefore, the approach should enable orchestration towards different constrained devices as well as high-capacity servers.

3.2 6G ORCHESTRATION PARADIGMS

New technology paradigms impacting 6G orchestration include:

- Intent-based orchestration where network operations are driven by high-level service requirements or business intents, which are then automatically translated into the necessary network configurations and resource allocations. Intent-based orchestration removes complexity and increases autonomy level.
- Multi-domain orchestration will be essential for delivering seamless end-to-end services in heterogeneous 6G infrastructure, which will span across

different technological domains (e.g., radio access network, transport network, core network) and potentially involve multiple administrative entities.

- Data-driven orchestration promises to improve the efficiency of management and orchestration processes that is essential when optimizing the cost-effectiveness of 6G network services.
- Edge-fog computing - strategic deployment of edge computing resources to bring processing closer to the user. Consequently, applications are distributed to locations that can be administered by different operators and that can have less physical and logical security protection. Hence, the expanding threat landscape requires additional confidentiality protection.
- AI-driven predictive resource allocation techniques to anticipate and preemptively manage the resource needs of latency-sensitive applications.
- Distributed orchestration architectures may be used to address scalability issues.
- Distributing AI capabilities closer to the network edge and potentially across different operator domains allows for faster and more localized decision-making, improving efficiency and responsiveness.

3.3 THREAT ANALYSIS

Security breaches in containerized and orchestrated systems can lead to severe consequences, including data loss, service disruptions, and significant reputational damage. This subsection identifies the main security threats and defines the threat models that are guiding our work.

3.3.1 MISBEHAVING INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDER / OPERATOR

The motivation for confidential computing emerges from the distrust towards the computing platform, i.e., towards the infrastructure and servers running the 6G services. It may be compromised or maintained by misbehaving infrastructure operators. In Table 2 we review some threats and mitigations related to infrastructure.

Table 2. Security threat related to misbehaving infrastructures

Threat	Description	Mitigations
Compromised misbehaving host	Confidential application code or data leaks from untrusted infrastructure. Reasons for compromise may be, e.g., an insider threat or	Confidential computing may be used to protect

	<p>exploitation of vulnerabilities in the container runtime or the host kernel.</p>	<p>deployments in use and at rest.</p> <p>Runtime security monitoring is needed to mitigate threats due to vulnerabilities in confidential computing approach.</p>
Compromised communication	<p>Code deployment and orchestration is vulnerable also during deployment and transmission of configurations.</p> <p>The orchestration system may be distributed and involve communication between different orchestration entities. Orchestration system may also be distributed over multiple administrative domains which may increase risks.</p>	<p>Cryptographic means can be used to protect deployments in transit as well as configuration transactions. This can be based, e.g., on secure mechanism like TLS protected configuration service running in confidential area or delivering a new confidential container for each new configuration.</p>
Network security misconfiguration	<p>Containerized microservices imply need to communicate with each other and external services. This communication is vulnerable for eavesdropping and interception. Microservices may also facilitate later movement of adversaries.</p>	<p>Network segmentation, monitoring, secure communication protocols</p>
Compromised infrastructure supply chain	<p>Misconfigured infrastructure relying on complex supply chains and third-party components</p>	<p>Supply chain security</p>
Vulnerabilities in orchestration platform	<p>Access to Kubernetes components like the API server may give adversary a control over all the running containers and their sensitive data. Misconfigurations are a typical source of vulnerabilities. Other include poor secrets management, poor role-based access control implementation, inadequate monitoring and insecure APIs. [17]</p>	<p>Securing the orchestration platform</p>
Orchestration systems leak information on customer applications	<p>Orchestration system may reveal business or customer critical information, e.g., what applications are used and how.</p>	<p>Securing the orchestration platform and orchestration transactions</p>

Distributed, multi-domain orchestration architecture extends threat landscape	In 6G, orchestration architecture may be more complex and distributed which may increase risk of a compromise. Similarly, multi-domain architectures will broaden threat landscape.	Verifying (remote attesting) mutually orchestrators and target platforms.
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3.3.2 MISBEHAVING TENANTS

Cloud and edge servers may be shared with multiple users and organization. As 6G services and applications come from different sources they have different security requirements and attributes. If one service is more vulnerable and becomes compromised, also the other tenants in the system may be compromised. Consequently, orchestration system should offer strong isolation not just between host and tenant but also between tenants.

Table 3. Security threats related to misbehaving tenants

Threat	Description	Mitigations
Tenant impacts or spies other tenants	An application may use the resources of other applications or collect information on identity or behaviour of other applications on the same servers.	Strong isolation and control on the use of shared resources.
Vulnerable containers	Containers are often built from base images sourced from public repositories, which may contain outdated software, known vulnerabilities, or even maliciously injected code. If these vulnerabilities are not identified and addressed, they can propagate to all containers instantiated from the compromised image, creating a widespread attack surface.	Regularly scanning container images for vulnerabilities and verifying their integrity and authenticity
Malicious images	Container image supply chain is a critical attack vector, leading to distribution of malicious or tampered images	Supply chain security. Protecting host platform and other tenants: The orchestrated applications should run with minimal privileges.
Run time security threats	Targeting running containers by injecting malicious code	API security, isolation
Privilege escalation attacks	E.g. container breakout, where an attacker manages to escape the isolated container environment and gain access to the underlying host system.	Strong tenant (VM/container) isolation and access control

3.3.3 SIDE-CHANNEL THREATS

At the core of confidential computing are TEEs, which provide a protected memory area, known as an enclave, for storing data and executing arbitrary code on an untrusted server. TEEs reduce the size of the Trusted Computing Base (TCB) and are designed to defend against adversaries with full system privileges, including root access. Essentially, they enable users to run containerized applications as usual, while preventing cloud providers or any compromised system software from inspecting, modifying or inferring any information about those applications. However, despite their strong isolation guarantees, TEEs have been subject to numerous attacks in recent years, particularly side-channel attacks.

Table 4. Side-channel threats

Threat	Description	Mitigations
Page-table attacks	These attacks exploit the fact that page tables, which map virtual to physical memory, remain under the control of the untrusted OS. This allows adversaries with OS-level access to launch side-channel attacks by revoking access permissions (e.g., marking pages as non-present) and observing page faults during enclave execution to infer fine-grained memory access patterns. In some cases, this leakage can expose sensitive data such as cryptographic keys. Additionally, attackers may manipulate page tables to redirect or influence enclave control flow, potentially enabling code-reuse or control-flow hijacking attacks.	Several countermeasures have been proposed to mitigate page-table attacks, including oblivious memory access, page access randomization, and fine-grained execution monitoring. Some defences eliminate observable page faults using hardware features like Intel TSX (e.g., T-SGX) or software padding to equalize memory access patterns. However, these techniques often incur performance overheads due to increased memory latency, transaction aborts, or added context-switching and instrumentation.
Cache attacks	Cache attacks exploit the fact that CPU cache hierarchies are shared across processes and privilege levels, including enclaves. By carefully measuring timing differences in memory accesses, attackers can infer whether specific cache lines were accessed by the victim, revealing sensitive information such as cryptographic keys or control flow decisions. Prominent techniques include <i>Flush+Reload</i> , which relies on shared memory and flush instructions to detect access patterns, and <i>Prime+Probe</i> , which monitors cache sets without	Mitigating cache side-channel attacks typically involves a combination of hardware isolation, software hardening, and execution-time defences. Hardware-based approaches include cache partitioning to isolate cache lines (e.g., between trusted and untrusted domains). Software-level mitigations include enforcing constant-time algorithms, avoiding secret-dependent memory accesses or obfuscating access patterns. Although these mitigations can be effective, they often introduce non-trivial performance overheads.

	requiring memory sharing, making it applicable to a broader range of settings.	
DRAM attacks	Dynamic Random-Access Memory (DRAM) attacks exploit low-level physical properties of memory hardware to induce unintended behaviour. The most well-known example is Rowhammer, which leverages the electrical interference caused by repeatedly accessing (or hammering) a specific row in DRAM to flip bits in adjacent rows. These bit flips can compromise memory regions that should be isolated, including enclave-protected data, effectively bypassing higher-level software and hardware protections.	Mitigating DRAM attacks typically involves a combination of hardware and system-level defences. At the hardware level, Error-Correcting Code (ECC) memory can detect and correct a limited number of bit flips before they become exploitable. Manufacturers have also introduced Target Row Refresh (TRR) mechanisms, which proactively refresh adjacent rows when repeated access patterns are detected. On the software side, memory allocation strategies can be employed to separate security-sensitive data from attacker-controlled regions in physical memory, thereby reducing the likelihood of effective bit flips. While hardware-based mitigations are increasingly common, many existing systems still lack comprehensive protections
Predictor attacks	Predictor attacks exploit microarchitectural components such as branch predictors and speculative execution engines, which are designed to improve CPU performance by predicting control flow and executing instructions ahead of time. In TEEs like Intel SGX, these mechanisms can be manipulated by untrusted code to cause speculative execution that accesses sensitive enclave data. Although the speculative instructions are later rolled back, microarchitectural side effects (e.g., cache state changes) may persist and be observed through side channels. Prominent examples include Spectre-type attacks, where an attacker mistrains the branch predictor to induce enclave mis-speculation and infer secrets	Mitigating predictor-based attacks involves both hardware-level protections and software-level hardening. On the hardware side, modern CPUs have introduced features to limit speculative execution across privilege boundaries. At the software level, developers can insert serialization instructions (e.g., LFENCE) to prevent speculation beyond sensitive branches. Additionally, microcode updates have been deployed by CPU vendors to patch known speculative vulnerabilities. While these mitigations are effective, they often come at a cost in execution latency and throughput, particularly in branch-heavy or performance-critical workloads.

3.3.4 ML-SPECIFIC THREATS

AI/ML Integration to orchestration will introduce new associated risks. First, they change the architecture increasing the complexity and exposing networks to new attack paths. ML algorithms are also prone to various security attacks, including data poisoning, model evasion, and inference attacks.

Table 5. Security challenges related to orchestration of ML and to use of ML in orchestration

Threat	Description	Mitigations
Information exposure	Privacy is a challenge when collecting large amounts of heterogeneous data. AI-driven orchestration systems collect private data which may leak. ML models may also be vulnerable and leak data/models.	Privacy preserving architectures for learning, such as federated learning
Undesirable configurations or abnormal behaviour	<p>The distributed and heterogeneous nature of 6G networks complicates the establishment of a common data processing pipeline for ML applications. Complexity may lead to vulnerabilities.</p> <p>AI-driven orchestration system, e.g. intent-based orchestration, may make unexpected decisions that are difficult to understand. AI systems are also susceptible for attack such as poisoning and evasion.</p>	Explainable AI, supply chain security, investing resources on security architecture design and verification
Attacks against automation components	Closed-loop network automation driven by AI may introduce security threats such as DoS attacks, man-in-the-middle attacks, and deception attacks	System and API security
Attacks against AI models	<p>Adversaries can target 6G/AI models by poisoning the data used for training, launching attacks during the learning and inference phases, and exploiting vulnerabilities in the model's APIs.</p> <p>Poisoning of the model by compromised clients or aggregators, may be easier in federated learning than in centralized learning due to the number of participating nodes, particularly if the security of nodes is not strongly assured and attested.</p>	System security, supply chain security, remote attestations.

4 ARCHITECTURE AND TECHNOLOGY ENABLERS FOR CONFIDENTIAL ORCHESTRATION

The section analyses architecture and technological building blocks for confidential orchestration. It describes an architecture for orchestration enabling us to provide structured view to confidential orchestration and analyse the available technology for 6G. The section also identifies and highlights gaps in the state-of-art and underlines potential solutions and areas needed further work.

In Section 4.1, we will first present a high-level framework – the enabling building blocks and their relations – for confidential orchestration. Then we will look more closely and analyse the technologies for the lower and upper parts of the framework: respectively, the confidentiality supporting infrastructure in Section 4.2 and the orchestration control in Section 4.3. Then in Section 4.4 we discuss how orchestration is related to the data sharing architecture and can be supported by several enabling technologies.

4.1 ARCHITECTURE

6G software orchestration is a cooperation between the controlling entities on the operators' side and computing assets on the infrastructure provider's side. An architectural view to the main elements – *the orchestration framework* – is illustrated in Figure 2. The main domains include the operator domain i.e., the owner and provider of confidential 6G applications and data in the upper part of the figure, and the infrastructure domain, which is hosting the confidential 6G software artefacts, in the lower part of the figure.

The trust model is highlighted with a trust boundary (dashed red line in the figure). In the upper side of the figure, we have a domain that is under operator's control: the operators' servers on the right and confidential containers on the left. In the lower side of the figure, we have infrastructure that is under the infrastructure provider's full control in right, or that is under operators' control through confidential computing technologies. The confidentiality of deployment can be based either on security hardware (here trusted containers and illustrated with light blue) or on cryptographic means (here encrypted containers and illustrated with dark blue). The separation of the basis of trust (encrypted vs. trusted containers) is illustrated with a blue dotted vertical line.

Figure 2. Confidential orchestration architecture

The infrastructure domain is based on the following components and enablers:

- Trusted containers – The hardware-secured containers will leverage available TEEs, which are integrated to container orchestration solutions, to isolate them from the host platform and other distrusted containers. A prominent trusted container approach is the Confidential Containers (CoCo) project.
- Encrypted containers – Software-based applications can be secured using advanced cryptographic means such as fully homomorphic cryptography.
- Infrastructure must also provide SW support for the containers (container system in the figure) by providing compatible CPU architecture, operating system, and container engine.

The operator's domain control components for orchestrating the services in the infrastructure. To emphasize the application-specific as well as dynamic nature of orchestration, we have divided the domain into four areas: 6G application as well as realms related to monitoring, analysis, and reactions.

Monitoring phase i.e. collecting data on the behaviour of infrastructure and security landscape. When considering confidential orchestration, platform integrity information becomes a key metric alongside the traditional performance related metrics. Remote attestation is a process where the application provider (attestor) can verify trustworthiness of target host and containerization systems before critical containers are deployed. It is a method where a host authenticates its hardware and software configuration to a remote party. Remote attestation involves the following architectural entities:

- Attester – the entity whose trustworthiness is being evaluated, i.e., the platform where containers are deployed.
- Relying party – the entity that needs to know the trustworthiness of the attestor, i.e., the entity deploying containers. E.g. Attestation Service at CoCo Trustee
- Verifier – entity evaluating evidence that the attestor provides. E.g., Key Broker Service at CoCo Trustee.
- Endorser – entity providing secure statements that vouch the integrity of the attestee's hardware and software. Typically, the manufacturer of edge/cloud hardware to where containers are deployed.

Analysis phase relates to making decisions on how the infrastructure deployment and configuration should be adjusted to support application and operator specific requirements and policies

- Orchestration intelligence – Applications can be orchestrated in different cloud, edge, and device platforms. Decisions where and when applications are scheduled to operate are based on operators' or application provider's needs and on available information on the infrastructure, e.g., on the host platform's capability or security health.

Reactions phase triggers deployments, configurations, and run books to deploy or configure services.

- Automated deployment, scaling, and management of 6G applications in confidential containers.

- Deployment of applications secured with privacy-preserving means
- Security orchestration – deploying or adjusting security applications¹

Secure control channel – Monitoring, deployment and configuration of containers requires secure services and secure communication between provider and host. Secure communication may also be required for different confidential containers.

4.2 INFRASTRUCTURE FOR CONFIDENTIALITY

Confidential containers, which were introduced in Section 2.3.1, can be deployed on various platforms ranging from cloud environments, such as Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud, and Amazon Web Services, as well as on different hardware architectures, including Intel TDX and SDX, AMD SEV, IBM Secure Execution, ARM CCA, and Hygon CSV. However, due to performance and resource constraints confidential containers are not feasible for every platform. For the cases where CoCo are unavailable confidential applications must be orchestrated using alternative strategies.

The CoCo consist of the following entities:

- Infrastructure (AWS, Azure etc.) provides compute resource for workloads
- Hardware TEES (Intel TDX and SGX, AMD SEV-SNP etc.) provide HW-based protection for data
- Hypervisor (e.g. KVM, QEMU, cloud hypervisor) manage (confidential) virtual machines
- Confidential computing services:
 - Attestation service (CoCo Trustee) validates hardware integrity
 - Key broker service (Coco Trustee) facilitates remote attestation
 - Key management service securely stores, manages, and backs up keys
 - Image build service (podman, buildah) build confidential containers and VS images
 - Image registry (Docker Hub, CSP registries etc.) store encrypted and signed container and VM images

¹Orchestration of 6G security applications – i.e. security orchestration – is a subset of 6G application orchestration. While this document mainly focuses to the security of orchestration also the security applications need to be orchestrated securely.

4.2.1 CONFIDENTIAL CONTAINERS ON CLOUD PLATFORMS

CoCo encapsulates pods within confidential virtual machines (CVMs), allowing cloud-native workloads to leverage confidential computing hardware with minimal modification. As CoCo's design philosophy prioritizes ease of use by abstracting away much of the hardware-dependent intricacies, it provides an accessible, platform-agnostic confidential computing solutions that can be easily adopted by mainstream cloud-native developers.

Intel Trust Domain Extensions (TDX) represent a significant advancement in Intel's confidential computing portfolio, becoming widely available with the 4th Generation Xeon Scalable Processors (Sapphire Rapids). TDX is specifically engineered to enhance the security and privacy of virtualized workloads within cloud environments by creating a TEE that isolates entire virtual machines (VMs) from the underlying physical hardware, including the operating system, hypervisor, and other co-located VMs.

AMD Secure Encrypted Virtualization-Secure Nested Paging (SEV-SNP) is a hardware-based confidential computing technology integrated into AMD EPYC processors from generation 3 and newer. As a virtualization-based confidential computing technology, SEV-SNP focuses on protecting a full confidential virtual machine (CVM) environment. AMD SEV-SNP supports running full operating systems within a CVM.

Intel TDX and AMD SEV-SNP are classified as VM-based TEEs, meaning they encrypt memory across a traditional VM boundary and operate atop a Virtual Machine Monitor (VMM). They share the overarching objective of removing cloud and infrastructure providers from the guest application's Trusted Computing Base (TCB), integrating natively with Kubernetes, and enabling the deployment of unmodified workloads

Intel Software Guard Extensions (SGX) is an earlier hardware-based technology that enables the creation of protected enclaves within memory, allowing only authorized application code to access sensitive data. Unlike full memory encryption technologies, SGX permits a specific application to establish its own protected enclave with a direct hardware interface, thereby limiting access and minimizing performance impact. SGX operates as a "process-based TEE," where a process requiring secure execution is logically divided into trusted and untrusted components.

Figure 3 illustrates two architectural alternatives for CoCo. The left alternative is based on lightweight VM, such as Kata containers, on TEE and provides strong

isolation boundaries. The right alternative isolates specific processes and leverages technologies like Intel SGX and requires modifications to applications but can produce smaller trusted computing base. To the control plane, CoCo introduces container image registry and services for key management and brokering. Further, CoCo provides attestation service to verify the integrity of the TEE and the software running within it [7].

Figure 3. Confidential Containers project defines two architecture alternatives (VM based in left and process based in right). The diagram adapted from the CoCo specification [8]

Workflow for VM-based TEEs approach encapsulates pods within confidential virtual machines (CVMs):

1. Workload preparation includes building container images using standard tools
2. Kubernetes deployment and scheduling towards hosts that support running confidential containers
3. Execution flow in TEEs is the following.
 - a. The confidential container runtime initiates VM TEE and launches a confidential virtual machine.

- b. Then an agent residing in newly launched enclave performs remote attestation to verify integrity of TEE.
- c. If the attestation is successful, the enclave agent obtains keys from the key broker service to verify and decrypt container images.
- d. The enclave's images management components download container images, which are pulled and unpacked inside the confidential guest and then verified and decrypted.
- e. Enclave starts the container workload to run inside protected environment.

4.2.1.1 PRINCIPLE OF LEAST PRIVILEGE

Principle of Least Privilege stands as a cornerstone of the security architecture, dictating that every entity, whether a human user, an automated process, or an individual machine—must be granted only the absolute minimum access rights required to perform its designated function, and no more. [68]

Core Principle: Every entity human, automated process, or machine is granted only the minimum access rights necessary for its specific function. This strategy is crucial for reducing the attack surface and limiting potential damage from breaches.

- Comprehensive Application: Principle of Least Privilege is applied across all layers of the system in the edge-cloud continuum, covering:
 - Human operators
 - Automated tasks
 - Individual computational nodes
- Confidential Containers & AI Workloads: For confidential containers, especially those running AI workloads in environments like Kubernetes, Principle of Least Privilege is strictly enforced through:
 - Pod Security Standards (PSSs): These impose tight security requirements on pods and containers, such as:
 - Running as non-root users.
 - Preventing shared host network or IPC namespaces.
 - Disallowing host filesystem mounts.

- Prohibiting the use of privileged or host ports. These restrictions significantly reduce the risk associated with containerized applications.
- Service Accounts: These provide granular control over pod permissions by assigning roles and permissions precisely tailored to each pod's functions and its processes.
- Zero Trust Networking: Security posture is further strengthened by integrating Zero Trust Networking principles:
 - Access is granted only after rigorous verification of both user and device credentials, regardless of origin. [69]
 - This approach eliminates ambient authority (e.g., direct root access) and ensures automated tooling does not implicitly extend its defined scope of authority.

CoCo fundamentally incorporates the principle of least privilege to enhance security by restricting access to confidential workloads from OS, hypervisor and cloud/infrastructure providers. On the other hand, the privileges of each container and its processes can also be minimized, preventing them from accessing or affecting other containers or the host system, thereby maintaining operational performance. By enforcing these granular controls, CoCo limits container exposure and risk.

4.2.1.2 GAPS IN CONFIDENTIAL CONTAINER TECHNOLOGIES

The current limitations on trusted container technology are:

- Self-signed certificate authority certificates for the container registry are not supported, meaning the container registry must use public CA signed certificates. This means that only public CA can be used.
- There is no support for encrypted container images.
- The container image is downloaded and executed inside the CVM (TEE). Currently, this image is also downloaded on the worker node, meaning that there is a container image double pull.
- Operating system support may be more limited.
- Additional overhead. Running applications on confidential containers will have penalties on performance and energy consumption.
- Confidential containers typically exhibit an increased pod startup time compared to standard pods.

4.2.2 CONFIDENTIAL CONTAINERS ON EDGE PLATFORMS

Confidential containers have specific requirements for the host platform. The hardware platform must provide sufficient memory and storage capacities, as well as support CPU architecture and operating system, which are supported by container technology. CoCo documentation [57] currently requires a minimum of 8GB RAM and 4 vCPU for the Kubernetes cluster node. Consequently, the CoCo project may not be directly applicable alternative for every situation and platform. In these cases, adaptations to the confidential application may be needed to enable a split architecture where only the most critical parts are executed in the secure world whereas the rest remain in the unsecure world.

This subsection describes approaches for orchestrating confidential code into different resource restricted edge/IoT-environments. We explore applicability and practical challenges on different confidentiality strategies for orchestration on five alternative platforms.

4.2.2.1 ORCHESTRATION ON ARM

Many ARM devices can support CoCo and thus in these cases the orchestration follows the same principles as in other platforms supporting CoCo.

ARM provides two architecture generations supporting confidential computations: the newer Confidential Compute Architecture (CCA) on ARMv9-A onwards and the older TrustZone since ARMv6-A. The primary isolation approach for confidentiality in CoCo on ARM CCA is hardware-based virtualization. TrustZone provides a hardware-enforced separation between two worlds: the normal world and the secure world. CCA is designed to be applicable across various markets and devices that utilize ARM microprocessors, including edge devices. CCA introduces the concept of "Realms," which are hardware-protected execution environments, and which facilitates seamless portability of confidential workloads across ARM-based devices. Realms builds upon the foundations of older generation TrustZone architecture but offers a more dynamic approach to isolation. Realms can operate alongside ARM's TrustZone technology, minimizing the need for significant modifications to existing trusted applications.

CoCo support for CCA is currently being developed [60][62]. In the recent release notes of CoCo (in version 0.8 [61]) CCA declared as untested or partially supported platform for CoCo with attestation.

CoCo can work directly on TrustZone but this requires adaptation (e.g. running a very stripped-down container runtime within the Secure World of TrustZone or

securing only specific container parts such as key management). CCA provides native hardware-based attestation, while TrustZone attestation is more limited mainly software based.

Running a CoCo application on ARM-based devices may necessitate some adaptations. First, the software and container runtime components need to be built or adapted to leverage features on ARM architecture and particular ARM device (specific hardware features may not be available for every device). Second, the attestation mechanisms used to verify the integrity of a confidential container on an ARM device will be specific to the ARM architecture and the platform.

4.2.2.2 ORCHESTRATION ON KEYSTONE RISC-V ENCLAVES

Keystone [42] is an open-source framework for building customizable TEEs using the RISC-V instruction set architecture. Keystone is often used in academic and research environments to explore and innovate in new confidential computing approaches.

Keystone builds on typical concepts of confidential computing: it provides isolated secure enclave for secret keys and data and platform integrity can be verified with remote attestation before orchestration. The Keystone monitor manages the execution context of the enclave. When application is started, the monitor securely loads the enclave code and data into the protected memory region. When the enclave's task is complete, it can be terminated, releasing the allocated resources. Interaction with the Keystone TEE and untrusted operating system or other enclaves happens through controlled channels managed by the Keystone monitor. These channels ensure data integrity and confidentiality during transfer. For more complex interactions, secure RPC mechanisms can be established. These protocols use cryptographic techniques to protect the confidentiality and integrity of the function calls and their parameters.

In the concept level Keystone TEEs can be seen as a platform that is compatible with the CoCo approach. It does not impose any limiting requirements. However, currently there are no known implementations available.

4.2.2.3 ORCHESTRATION ON OP-TEE

Open Portable Trusted Execution Environment (OP-TEE) [41] is a minimal TEE operating system designed for security-critical tasks in isolation. Its primary function is to host small, specific trusted applications that perform secure computations and manage sensitive data. Devices that use OP-TEE are typically

designed with both a rich execution environment and an isolated OP-TEE running concurrently on the same hardware.

OP-TEE is not designed to run arbitrary, potentially large, containerized applications. OP-TEE environments typically have very limited resources (memory, storage) compared to the Rich Execution Environment (REE) where container runtimes operate. Running a full container with its bundled libraries and dependencies would likely exceed these limitations.

OP-TEE could be seen as one of the underlying TEE technologies that Confidential Containers might leverage, especially in scenarios where the deployment target has ARM TrustZone capabilities. However, applying CoCo on OP-TEE is challenging due to resource constraints. OP-TEE environments are typically very resource-constrained compared to the environments where full container runtimes operate. Running a complete container runtime and container within OP-TEE would likely exceed these limitations.

Instead of running an entire application as a container in OP-TEE, application could be decomposed so that parts that require strong security guarantees are put into smaller, dedicated Trusted Applications. These TAs could then interact with the containerized main application running in the non-secure world via the TEE Client API. The application can be run in a container and could interact with the trusted applications running within OP-TEE on the same device for enhanced security of certain functions. For example, a container might rely on a TA in OP-TEE for hardware-backed key generation and storage.

4.2.2.4 ORCHESTRATION ON FPGA TEES

Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) are increasingly used in edge computing due to their performance and energy efficiency. They can support 6G by providing specialized and reconfigurable hardware for processing signals and supporting AI-native applications with ultra-low latency. Recently, several FPGA-based TEE approaches have been proposed [44][45][46].

Software loading to TEE can be based on different approaches:

- Secure boot and chain of trust - similar to traditional secure boot processes, a smaller signed boot loader withing FPGA TEE may verify the next stage of software, which then verifies the next phase and so forward.
- Direct loading – FPGA TEE may hand secure interfaces that can be used to load software and data into FPGA memory. For instance, FPGA may be running a TLS server which authenticates the sources of software and then

enables software uploads. Interfaces may be also towards a rich execution environment (general purpose processes which may be residing on alongside the FPGA) or over-the-air interfaces.

4.2.2.5 ORCHESTRATION ON SEAL-EMBEDDED DEVICES

Resource-constrained embedded devices without trusted execution can support confidential computation with homomorphic encryption. Microsoft SEAL-Embedded [58][59] is a lightweight and optimized version of Microsoft SEAL (Simple Encrypted Arithmetic Library) specifically designed for resource-constrained embedded devices, particularly those in the Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystem. It is designed to run on resource constrained processors (demonstrated with ARM Cortex-M4 and Cortex-A7) with limited RAM and flash memory (in the order of 100 KB).

Runtime configuration of applications secured with SEAL-Embedded is limited. It is targeted for very small applications and dynamic configuration would imply more complex software and higher memory usage. However, applications could have preprogrammed options that are triggered through simple interface. For significant changes in application behaviour, the more feasible approach is to deploy a new version of the application.

4.3 CONTROL OVER CONFIDENTIAL ORCHESTRATION

Confidential computing paradigm provides opportunities for optimizing the security of 6G systems. The operators can find trusted infrastructure that fulfils better the requirements related to their confidential workloads. On the other hand, managing the confidentiality dimension also complicates orchestration processes.

4.3.1 INTELLIGENCE FOR ORCHESTRATION

The increasing number of dynamic mission-critical 6G applications necessitates a shift towards more adaptive and intelligent resource management. Traditional orchestration and scheduling methods, which often rely on predefined resource requests and limits, may not always accurately reflect the dynamic nature of application workloads. This leads to scenarios where resources are either underutilized or where contention arises, impacting application performance. The incorporation of runtime metrics into the scheduling process allows for a more nuanced understanding of actual workload behaviour, enabling the system to make more informed decisions about where and when to run specific tasks. This evolution signifies a step towards a more mature phase of resource orchestration, where

optimization is driven by real-time operational data rather than just declared intentions.

Integration of runtime metrics into scheduling can support self-optimizing orchestration environments. When workload performance, as indicated by metrics such as latency, CPU throttling, memory pressure, or platform integrity/trustworthiness directly influences future placement decisions, the cluster can continuously adapt to ensure optimal performance, resource utilization, and security. For instance, if a particular type of workload consistently exhibits poor performance on a specific node configuration, a metric-aware scheduler can learn from this pattern and avoid placing similar workloads on such nodes in the future.

AI is an enabler for simplifying software orchestration in several ways:

- Large Language Models (LLMs) can assist in generating and validating initial service orchestration blueprints based on high-level business or service goals. This can significantly reduce the manual effort involved in defining orchestration logic.
- AI-powered monitoring tools can provide deeper insights into the performance of orchestrated systems, identify bottlenecks, and predict problems.
- Intent-driven service orchestration paradigms provide simplified user interface for operators to define requirements whose run-time execution and enforcement is then left for the responsibility of AI.

4.3.2 ORCHESTRATION METRICS

Orchestration can be driven by static configuration and policies but also by run-time measurements. Orchestration adapts the 6G system – defines where code is executed and when – according to different parameters and runtime metrics including [38]:

- CPU utilization indicates the percentage of CPU time being used by pods and nodes, providing a direct measure of computational demand.
- Memory usage reflects the amount of RAM being consumed, highlighting potential memory pressure or leaks.
- Network traffic metrics track the volume of data (in bytes) sent and received, which can be indicative of data-intensive applications or inter-service communication.

- Disk I/O metrics, such as read and write operations and throughput, reveal the level of disk activity and can point to workloads with significant data storage or processing requirements.
- Pod status metrics, such as running, pending, failed, and ready conditions, provide information about the operational state of applications.
- Restart Counts for containers within Pods can signal instability or underlying issues, potentially related to resource constraints.
- Application-level performance KPIs, such as Request Latency, which measures the time taken by applications to process requests, Error Rates, which quantifies the proportion of unsuccessful requests, and Throughput, which indicates the number of requests an application can handle over a given period.

In addition to the common metrics the orchestration should consider

- Trustworthiness and integrity of nodes
- Security situation in nodes
- Security policies and requirements for different workloads

In addition to consider the metrics that describe the infrastructure, it is important to consider how trustworthy they are and do they contain privacy critical information. Confidential computing and remote attestation are enablers for enhancing and assuring that the parameters of orchestration can be trusted. Further, privacy enhancing technologies and e.g. federated learning can have a role to assure the privacy of the parameters.

4.3.3 REMOTE ATTESTATION AND ORCHESTRATION

Before any confidential workload is permitted to access sensitive data, its execution environment *must* undergo a rigorous attestation process. Attestation provides cryptographic proofs and verifiable evidence, such as signatures or hashes, which ensure the integrity of the software stack and confirm that it is running untampered within the TEE. This process offers fundamental guarantees about the Trusted Computing Base (TCB), the isolation properties of the environment, and the root of trust of the enclave.

Remote attestations occur when software is deployed. However, as TEEs are not immune to vulnerabilities, the ability to remotely attest the platform's state, including applied patches and microcode versions, is critical for maintaining a continuous chain of trust and verifying that known vulnerabilities have been addressed. This extends the importance of attestation beyond initial setup to

ongoing operational assurance in a dynamic threat landscape. In secure orchestration settings, attestation should be done also before any configuration or orchestration transaction occurs. When considering, for instance, orchestration in the context of federated learning applications, the FL aggregator could verify integrity of clients each time when they are sending model updates (e.g., gradients, weight changes). Similarly, clients can verify identity and trustworthiness of the aggregator when it is distributing the global model and its updates.

4.3.3.1 THE PROTOCOL FOR REMOTE ATTESTATION

Remote Attestation is a critical security mechanism that enables a remote party, known as the Relying Party, to verify the integrity and authenticity of an application running within a TEE. This process is fundamental for establishing trust in distributed environments where trust cannot be implicitly assumed, ensuring that sensitive data or operations are only entrusted to genuinely secure and uncompromised systems. [70]

Figure 4. Attestation workflow

The standard RA workflow, as architecturally outlined in RFC9334, involves an Attester (the TEE or the device hosting it) generating Evidence about its current state. This evidence typically includes cryptographic measurements of the hardware, firmware versions, and hash digests of the software stack running within the TEE. This evidence is then conveyed to a Verifier, which appraises it against predefined policies and a set of trusted reference values. Based on this appraisal, the Verifier generates Attestation Results. The Relying Party then utilizes these results to make an informed decision on whether to consider the Attester trustworthy and subsequently release confidential data or authorize sensitive operations.

4.3.3.2 TRUSTEE

The CoCo Trustee project [77][78] provides a suite of tools and components designed for attesting confidential guests and securely delivering secrets to them. Although developed primarily for the CoCo project, its design allows for compatibility with a wide variety of applications and hardware platforms.

Key components of the Trustee project include:

- *Key Broker Service* (KBS) functions as the relying party in the RATS model, orchestrating the verification and release of sensitive information.
- *Attestation Service* verifies the evidence provided by the TEE. In the RATS model, this component acts as the Verifier, assessing the authenticity and integrity of the attestation report.
- *Reference Value Provider Service* manages the reference values that are used by the Attestation Service to verify TEE evidence. These reference values represent the expected, known-good state of the TEE and its software components.
- *KBS Client Tool* is a utility designed for testing or configuring the KBS and AS, facilitating their setup and management.

Within the confidential VM or enclave (the guest environment), two additional components play crucial roles:

- *Attestation Agent* is responsible for obtaining the raw hardware evidence from within the guest TEE, which is then sent to KBS for verification.
- *Confidential Data Hub* handles confidential operations within the guest, including initiating requests for secrets from KBS.

4.3.3.3 SECURE DISTRIBUTED MULTI-DOMAIN ORCHESTRATION

Software orchestration in 6G networks includes the distribution of control logic across different operator domains. To deliver seamless end-to-end services across different administrative and technological domains (belonging to different operators or service providers), the control logic needs to span these domains. This enables coordinated management of resources and services that involve multiple stakeholders.

Secure cooperation between different domains can be based on different approaches. For instance, the zero-trust principle emphasizes the need to authenticate and authorize all cross-domain transactions. Techniques such as secure multi-party computation and distributed ledger technology can provide, respectively, confidentiality and integrity to the transactions. TEEs provide a complementary approach that can be used to protect the orchestration control logic when distributed across domains, ensuring confidentiality and integrity.

Figure 5. Attestation as an enabler for maintaining trust over multi-domain orchestration

4.4 SECURE DATA SHARING ACROSS MULTIPLE ENTITIES

For enabling confidential data exchange in complex collaborative AI settings, the leveraging of Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) and Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC) is paramount. These techniques allow joint computation over private inputs without ever disclosing the raw data, which is fundamental for applications like federated threat intelligence where multiple organizations collaborate on shared insights without revealing their proprietary data. [73]

Beyond the cryptographic protection of data in use, ensuring Data Provenance and Integrity is a critical security and trust component in distributed AI systems. Data provenance involves meticulously tracking the movements and transformations of each data point from its origin onward, creating a transparent, documented, and cryptographically bound record of its complete history. [74]

This immutable trail is vital for preventing data tampering, designing inherently trustworthy systems, detecting anomalies or inconsistencies, and ensuring auditability and regulatory compliance.

Provenance systems function by tagging newly digitized information with rich metadata, such as time, date, location, origination device type, and privacy rights, and cryptographically binding this information to the data. This metadata is then updated and rebounds at every subsequent transformation point throughout the data's lifecycle.

Emerging technologies such as blockchains and other distributed ledgers [studied in CONFIDENTIAL6G Deliverable 4.2] are ideally suited for underpinning these tamper-proof provenance systems due to their inherent immutability and distributed consensus mechanisms, which create an unbroken chain of trust.

Collaborative AI, particularly Federated Learning, inherently addresses the raw data sharing privacy problem but introduces a new set of complex challenges related to model integrity, communication efficiency, and data heterogeneity. This indicates that privacy-preserving collaboration in AI extends beyond simply not sharing raw data. It critically involves ensuring the integrity, authenticity, and trustworthiness of the model updates and the derived insights shared among participants.

An effective orchestration framework for complex collaborative AI must therefore integrate advanced secure aggregation techniques (e.g., FHE, SMPC) to protect model updates during aggregation, optimized communication protocols (e.g., model compression) to mitigate bandwidth issues, and, crucially, robust data provenance mechanisms (potentially leveraging blockchain or distributed ledger technology [studied in CONFIDENTIAL6G Deliverable 4.2]) to cryptographically bind metadata to model updates and intermediate results. This allows participants to verify the origin, transformations, and integrity of the AI models and shared features, enabling detection and prevention of malicious training or data poisoning attacks. This moves the focus from merely "privacy" to a broader "trustworthiness of the entire collaborative AI pipeline".

Figure 6: Secure decentralized data sharing framework

Secure decentralized data sharing framework [CONFIDENTIAL6G Deliverable 4.2] is as explained below:

- Edge Layer:
 - This is the layer where the data is generated and consumed. It includes devices like IoT devices, user devices, etc. These devices interact with the system using secure protocols.
- Confidential Networking Layer:
 - This layer is responsible for secure communication between devices and the system. It uses post-quantum cryptography and other enhanced cryptographic protocols to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of the data in transit.
- Confidential Orchestration Layer:
 - This layer is responsible for managing the overall flow of data in the marketplace.
- Computation Layer:

- This layer is where the computations on the data happen. It uses technologies like Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC), Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs), and Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) to perform computations on encrypted data, ensuring the privacy of the data.
- Application Layer
- Data Ops:
 - This layer is responsible for managing the data lifecycle, including data acquisition, storage, and preprocessing.
- DLT Layer

5 PROOF-OF-CONCEPTS AND EXPERIMENTS FOR CONFIDENTIAL ORCHESTRATION

This section describes our experiences with the implemented concepts for confidential orchestration.

5.1 TESTING AND EVALUATION

The process of testing is the evaluation of components taking into account specified functional platform requirements. The goal is to identify and rectify bugs, deficiencies, unexpected behaviour and to timely provide corrective measures. We should stress the fact that the testing procedures described in this deliverable will be performed on a technical level, by the development teams of the project themselves and not by real users.

Testing in a pilot operation of the platform, falls within the scope of WP5 and will be elaborated there. However, we plan a small-scale testing operation in the context of WP4, which we describe in this deliverable.

Testing is, usually, performed on two levels:

- i) Individual module
- ii) Integrated system testing.

The former refers to the testing of the individual system components with respect to the requirements and the latter refers to the testing of the integrated system itself by assessing the interfaces among the modules and the involved data flow and the expected behaviour of the system “as a whole.”

In order to effectively manage the complexity of the final system, testing will be initially performed on an individual module basis before the integration begins. After all modules are verified, then the integration will begin and when it is completed, a final set of tests will be performed mainly in the form of a small-scale pilot operation.

5.1.1 TESTING PROCEDURE DEVELOPMENT

Our initial test plan is based on the following general considerations:

- *The adoption of a strategy to use. When testing the integrated modules and how the tests will be conducted (i.e., use cases). Our consortium has decided on the adopted methodology which is explained in this deliverable.*

- *What will be tested* - (e.g., software modules against set requirements). The modules that will be tested are described within the context of WP4.
- *What will be the time-frame* of the testing (e.g., when it starts and ends). We have followed the task and WP sequencing as described in the DoA (WP4 and WP5).
- *Testing responsibilities among involved parties*. These responsibilities have already been assigned and follow the corresponding module design and development responsibilities as described in the DoA, especially in WP4.
- *Pass and fail conditions for each performed test*. The partners have proposed themselves the described tests for the modules they developed and thus, have identified accurately these conditions.
- *Potential risks involved when a test is performed*. Actually, no privacy or other risk is foreseen for the described tests as they will be conducted in a restricted context and controlled environment by the involved partners.
- *Approval of the testing plan from all involved parties*. All parties have agreed on the tests and the testing plan as described in this deliverable.

5.1.2 TESTING METHODOLOGY

CONFIDENTIAL6G has decided to adopt an agile testing approach. Briefly, this approach considers testing and development as two intertwined phases and not sequential (i.e., testing following development). This decision was dictated by the tight delivery dates of the modules as well as the requirement for early integration before the use case testing of WP5 takes place.

With respect to the practical, separate, and integrated module testing, the generic methodology proposed in will be followed.

With respect to system testing, there are generally two main methodologies:

- (i) Incremental testing,
- (ii) Non-incremental testing

Incremental testing includes several methods:

- Bottom-Up approach – this method starts with testing the lower-level components, allowing early detection of issues. It needs drivers to simulate higher-level components that are not yet developed.
- Top-Down approach – this method tests the highest-level components first, focusing on the system functionalities, data flows, and interfaces. It

minimizes the need for drivers but requires stubs to simulate unavailable lower-level modules.

- Hybrid integration – this approach combines Top-Down and Bottom-Up testing. Lower-level modules are tested in parallel with their integration into the system, reducing the need for stubs and drivers but requiring more operators' actions to ensure smooth operation.

We will use the hybrid integration testing approach, in which lower-level modules are tested in parallel with their integration. This means that as modules are integrated, they are also tested simultaneously. Consequently, the need for stubs and drivers is minimized. However, this approach is a bit less systematic than the Top-Down and Bottom-Up approaches and may require more coordination effort.

The testing procedures for the project components defined will be further described in a uniform way, by providing templates for each of the testing use cases. The se case templates are beneficial because they ensure consistency, clarity, and efficiency in documenting and executing test procedures. They guarantee that all use cases are documented in the same way, making them easier to read and understand. By using templates, relevant details are systematically gathered and organized, reducing the possibility of errors.

The proposed template has two sections: Use Case Identification and Use Case Definition. The template was presented at CONFIDENTIAL6G Deliverable D4.2.

5.1.3 A TEST CASE FOR BASELINE CONFIDENTIAL ORCHESTRATION

This test case describes the baseline scenario for orchestrating confidential workloads.

Table 6. Secure deployment of application using confidential containers – use case identification

Use Case ID:	VTT: CoCo:01	
Use Case Name:	Use Case 1 – Deployment of security critical application using Confidential Container and Kubernetes	
Created By:	Andrea Dalla Costa, Jani Suomalainen, Markku Kylänpää	Last Updated By:
Date Created:	03.06.2024.	Date Last Updated:

Table 7. Secure deployment of application using confidential containers – use case definition

Actors:	Confidential application, Kubernetes operator (the end user making tests), infrastructure provider, infrastructure operator
Description:	This test should ensure that confidential application is correctly scheduled and executed on the target Kubernetes node with support for TEE. Deployment is done by a Kubernetes operator (the user) to the trusted infrastructure, which is provided by the infrastructure provider. The infrastructure operator cannot access the application. Optionally, the target platform integrity can be remote attested before deployment.
Trigger:	Confidential workload is set to be deployed. Kubernetes and confidential containers are used.
Preconditions:	A Kubernetes cluster has been setup with at least one node providing support for confidential containers. The Kubernetes template that describes the confidential workload is properly configured, with the correct execution runtimes selected.
Postconditions:	The workflow is successfully scheduled and deployed to a node with TEE support. The confidential application is running correctly.
Normal Flow:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Workload Preparation - building of container images using standard tools (e.g. podman or Docker) 2. Kubernetes template preparation 3. Kubernetes deployment and scheduling towards hosts that support running confidential containers (applying templates describing the container and run time) 4. Execution flow in TEEs is the following. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Confidential container runtime initiates VM TEE and launches a confidential virtual machine. b. Optional: an agent residing in newly launched enclave performs remote attestation to verify integrity of TEE. c. Optional: If the attestation is successful, the enclave agent obtains keys from the key broker service to verify and decrypt container images. d. The enclave's images management components download container images, which are pulled and unpacked inside confidential guest and then verified and decrypted. e. Enclave starts the container workload to run inside protected environment.
Alternative Flows:	
Exceptions:	Attestation verification errors (should lead to deployment being aborted). Infrastructure errors (like nodes going offline) or resource exhaustion may prevent orchestration.

Includes:	
Special Requirements:	
Legal Considerations:	

5.2 CONFIDENTIAL CONTAINERS FOR FEDERATED LEARNING ON EDGE AND IOT PLATFORMS

To understand and improve the feasibility of CoCo on embedded, resource restricted platforms, we built a test environment and profiled computing costs and energy consumption of a critical AI application.

The measurement results alongside with an orchestration approach (described in Section 5.3), have been demonstrated at the Democompo'2025 event at Oulu, Finland on May 2025 [75], at EuCNC 2025 at Poznan, Poland on June 2025 [76], and at HAIC Secure Systems Demo Day 2025 at Espoo, Finland on June 2025 [79]. The demonstrations were accompanied by a poster *Confidential Containerized Federated Learning for Distributed Security*.

5.2.1 THE USE CASE

As the background use case, we considered privacy threats against federated learning. FL is a prominent AI solution for private critical data but vulnerable for malicious aggregating nodes. In FL local nodes do not share their privacy critical data but gradients which are used by an aggregating node to create a global model. However, in the Improved Gradient Leakage attack (iDLG) [47] an adversary is able to reconstruct the private data from shared gradients.

Figure 7. Layered view to the architecture for confidential federated learning on 6G

We demonstrated two privacy-enhancing approaches to mitigate this attack: Differential Privacy (DP) and TEE. In the first, noise is added to the gradients to make reconstruction difficult. In the second, the aggregating node is secured using confidential container to prevent adversary gaining access to gradients. The approaches have slightly different threat models (in the CoCo case the aggregating node is assured to be trustworthy, in the DP case the aggregating node can be malicious) and they also introduce different types of costs (both in terms of degraded accuracy of AI as well as additional computation and loss of energy). Figure 7 illustrates the concepts we compared and demonstrated in a layered architecture view. The studied alternative confidentiality solutions are illustrated in green layers in the figure.

We used a FL application for a basic image classification task. We trained a two-layer Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model with 128 hidden layers using the Federated Extended MNIST (FEMNIST) dataset [67] available with the FederatedScope platform [66]. The dataset includes 62 classes of handwritten characters and digits, covering uppercase and lowercase letters as well as digits from 0 to 9. The FL setup consisted of three distributed clients and one server. The training was conducted over 300 rounds, with an early stopping patience of 100 and a learning rate of 0.01. Notably, the early stopping threshold, learning rate and the number of hidden layers in the CNN model can influence energy consumption.

5.2.2 TEST SETUP AND METHODS

The costs of proposed mitigations – the consumption of energy and computing resources and degradation of AI accuracy – were explored with regular and Confidential Containers on ARM platform.

5.2.2.1 BACKGROUND ON ENERGY PROFILING ON TEEs

Profiling behaviour and performance of trusted applications with standard profiling tools is challenging as the security hardware prevents profiling software – living in unsecured world – from seeing what is happening in the secure world. The accurate measurements can be done using hardware e.g., ampere meters, which see trusted applications as a black box and cannot provide granular analysis, or with trusted measurement software, which are living in the same secure world as the measured object, and which hence can then impact to the measurements.

Several SW tools for performance measurements on TEEs have been presented. Early approaches [50][51] for Intel SGX rely on timestamps outside TEE. TS-perf [52] and TEE-perf [53] where the latter is available as open-source tool, provide function-level performance profiling and are based on compiler instrumentation. Existing measurements efforts on ARM TrustZone include Amacher et al. [49] who provided performance and energy analysis using the OP-TEE framework. Wang et al. [48] analysed performance of TEE based encryption and proposed an energy-efficient strategy (ETS-TEE) for scheduling and offloading trusted applications between a mobile device and edge server. They evaluated the strategy with Raspberry Pi 3B as the local mobile device and AI-optimized Jetson TX2 as the edge server.

Hua et al. [65] measured overhead for the execution time of their own TZ-containers on ARM TrustZone. They reported an overhead close to 5%.

Existing performance analysis of FL on TEEs include work by Casell et al. [54]. They benchmarked FL training inside Intel SGX environments and measured runtimes.

5.2.2.2 TEST ENVIRONMENT

Our test environment is described in Figure 8. We measured execution time and energy consumption of federated learning client applications both on confidential containers as well as on regular (non-confidential) containers. In our setup we used two Raspberry Pi 4 Model B devices with 8GB of ram. Both devices are enrolled as workers in a Kubernetes cluster, with all the control layer components of the cluster running in a dedicated VM on a separate server.

To prepare for the measurement tests, we first created the required container images. Since the federated learning clients will be executed on the Raspberry devices, the images must be compatible with the *aarch64* architecture. In order to achieve this, the images can be built on an *aarch64* device, for example directly on

the Raspberry devices as we did, or it is also possible to cross-compile them on an *amd64* platform using emulation with QEMU.

Once the images are built, they should be made available on an image registry that the Kubernetes cluster is able to access. In our case we used *DockerHub*, the most popular image registry[64].

To deploy the containers on the Kubernetes cluster we created the required template files, which specify the details of the containers. For our tests, the templates defined four pods, one for the federated learning server and the other three for the clients.

Moreover, while measuring energy consumption we wanted to have only one client being executed on each Raspberry device, with the third client and server component of the federated learning application deployed on a different Kubernetes worker, which was set up similarly to the control-layer side of the cluster. To achieve this, we forced the scheduling of each container to its designated worker by setting the *nodeName* field in the templates. This is not required for normal deployments but was needed for our power measurement test runs.

The last configuration step required is to specify in the template the runtime that should be used to execute the container, which toggles the usage of confidential containers or regular containers. This is achieved by setting the *runtime-handler* annotation and *runtimeClassName* fields in the templates. If these values are not provided, the default runtime will be used, resulting in regular containers being executed.

This is the only modification required to execute the confidential containers, and no further customization of the container image is required.

We executed the federated learning application by deploying the prepared templates, and we recorded the execution time, repeating the process multiple times both with normal containers and with confidential containers.

At the same time, we measured the energy consumption of FL nodes on ARM devices using external hardware measuring device: Otii Ace Pro [55]. It is an instrument that serves as a portable power supply and a precise current and voltage measurement unit. It provides measurements on energy consumption with a sampling rate up to 50 kilo samples per second. The device was set up as the power supply of the Raspberry device and thus measuring the total power consumed by the device during the different executions. The energy consumption

data presented were recorded from the same device because there was a small but noticeable difference between different Raspberry devices.

Figure 8. Test setup for measuring energy consumption of CoCo on ARM

We measured the energy consumption of FL nodes on ARM devices using external hardware measuring device: Otii Ace Pro [55]. It is an instrument that serves as a portable power supply and a precise current and voltage measurement unit. It provides measurements on energy consumption with a sampling rate up to 50 kilo samples per second.

5.2.3 RESULTS: ENERGY AND COMPUTING OVERHEAD

Table 8. Energy and time overhead due to Confidential Containerization on ARM devices

Container	Power (mWh)	Overhead Power	Avg Time (s)	Overhead Time
Regular container on Raspberry Pi	289	100%	273.67	100%
CoCo on Raspberry Pi	299	104.18%	283.84	103.71%

Table 8 presents the results of the measurement that we observed during our test executions. For both energy consumption and execution time the CoCo setup showed a small but noticeable overhead of about 4% compared to regular containers, while running on the same Raspberry device.

The overhead might be dependent on the specific application being deployed and could change slightly, but our measurements is in line with previous results, including [65].

5.3 TRUST AND SUSTAINABILITY AWARE SCHEDULING ON CLOUD-EDGE CONTINUUM

To optimize the security and to minimize the costs of services operating on dynamic 6G environment (where availability of different computing resources varies in time) the orchestration system needs to make intelligent and adaptive decisions. We studied means to increase the intelligence the orchestration decision making, i.e., developed capability to adapt orchestration based on changing infrastructure and confidentiality and sustainability requirements from the operators. In particular, we designed and experimented with Kubernetes scheduling to prioritize infrastructure nodes that are trustworthy and able to fulfil requirements with minimal processing and energy costs.

Our concept for adaptive prioritization is illustrated in Figure 9. It shows orchestrators capability to collect security posture or health, and performance related data from the infrastructure and, based on that and available policies and sustainability profiles, prioritize scheduling decisions. We utilize the energy profiling we described in Section 5.2 as a knowledge base. The CoCo attestation features, Trustee, can also be utilized as a source of platform security health information.

Figure 9. High-level architecture for security and sustainability-driven orchestration

5.3.1 K8S SCHEDULING

The default Kubernetes scheduler, known as kube-scheduler [33][34], is a core component of the control plane responsible for assigning pods to nodes for execution. Its decision making has three phases: filtering, scoring, and selection.

During the filtering phase, the scheduler identifies a set of feasible nodes that meet the Pod's specific requirements. These requirements can include node's security and trustworthy software configuration, node selectors and node affinity rules, and taints and tolerations. For example, if a pod requests a certain software configuration, which is attested to be correct, as well as CPU and memory capacity, the scheduler will filter out any nodes that do not meet the criteria.

Once the filtering step is complete, the scheduler proceeds to the scoring phase. In this phase, the feasible nodes are ranked based on various criteria to determine the most suitable placement for the pod. The scoring process considers factors such as resource utilization, Pod affinity and anti-affinity rules, topology spread constraints, and custom scoring plugins which can indicate, e.g., energy and security rules. Pod affinity rules can encourage the scheduler to place a Pod on a node where related Pods are already running, while anti-affinity rules can prevent co-location of certain Pods.

After scoring all the feasible nodes, the scheduler selects the node with the highest score and binds the pod to it, notifying the API server of this decision.

Additionally, Kubernetes provides several built-in features that allow users to influence the scheduling of Pods based on various criteria, including their importance and node characteristics. PriorityClasses and pre-emption offer a mechanism to prioritize certain workloads over others. [35] Node Affinity and Node Selectors provide ways to constrain Pods to run on specific nodes based on labels applied to those nodes. [36] nodeSelector is a simple mechanism, allowing users to specify a set of key-value pairs that must match labels on the target node. nodeAffinity offers a more flexible and expressive syntax for defining rules.

Below we have a simple example nodeAffinity YAML-syntax, which prioritizes nodes with high security level and good energy-efficiency. The prioritization gives more weight to the security level (80), while the weight for efficiency is 20. The levels are specified for nodes as labels (e.g. *kubectl label nodes my-worker-node security.level=high*).

Table 9. Example Kubernetes configuration syntax for prioritizing security and energy efficiency in scheduling

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: Pod
metadata:
  name: C6G-app
spec:
  affinity:
```

```
nodeAffinity:
  preferredDuringSchedulingIgnoredDuringExecution:
  - weight: 80
    preference:
      matchExpressions:
      - key: security.level
        operator: In
        values:
        - high
  - weight: 20
    preference:
      matchExpressions:
      - key: energyefficiency
        operator: Gt # higher value means more efficient values:
        - "7"
containers:
- name: C6G-container
  image: C6G-image
```

Taints and Tolerations [37] control which pods can be scheduled on specific nodes. A taint is applied to a node and repels any Pod that does not have matching toleration. Tolerations are specified in the Pod specification and allow a Pod to be scheduled on a node with a matching taint.

Kubernetes components for collecting metrics include *kubelets*, which run on each worker node and collect resources usage statistics, and the *metrics server*, which aggregates usage data in a cluster. *Kube-state-metrics* provides state information on Kubernetes objects from the API server.

5.3.2 SCHEDULER CUSTOMIZATION

The default scheduler has certain limitations. It primarily relies on static configurations and resource requests, which may not accurately reflect the dynamic resource demands of applications at runtime. It lacks built-in capabilities to directly incorporate real-time runtime metrics, such as actual CPU utilization or network latency, into its decision-making process. Also, the default scheduler typically runs as a single instance, which can become a bottleneck in large clusters with a high volume of scheduling requests.

The Kubernetes scheduling framework [39] enables development of customized scheduling logic. It is based on a pluggable architecture, which allows scheduling features to be implemented as plugins, which can be connected to several extension points. Registered plugins are then invoked during the scheduling

process to offer granular control over orchestration. Scheduling plugins access run-time metrics by integrating with external monitoring tools.

5.3.3 PRIORITIZATION BASED ON METRICS FOR CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

To drive the orchestration based on the features and quality of the confidential computation approach, we defined the following metrics. These metrics can be used to label the infrastructure nodes with TEE.

Table 10. Metrics for Confidential Container security and example levels

Category	Metric	Levelling example
Confidential container	CoCo architecture can be process or VM based. With VM based the isolation may be stronger as HW-backed virtualization provides more robust security boundary. With VM-based the trusted computing base is also typically smaller. Process based isolation trade these security advances for performance.	0 – no CoCo support 1 – process based containerization 2 – VM based containerization
Isolation	Strength of isolation between TEE from REE. Measurement is typically based on SW and HW analysis by a trusted party.	0 – unknown, weak 1 – mediocre 2 – strong
	Memory isolation – How memory of trusted application is secured from other processes. The isolation strength depends on threat model and assumptions.	1 – HW based memory isolation (partitioning) 1 – Enclaves (memory isolation within user space) 1 – Memory encryption 1 – Memory integrity protection 2 – Combination (to prevent logical and physical memory attacks)
	CPU isolation – How TEE's execution is protected from interference of other processes. The isolation strength depends on threat model and assumptions.	2 – Hardware partitioning 2 – Enclave 2 – Memory encryption
Remote attestation	Attestation completeness - what aspects of the TEE's state are included in the attestation report.	1 – operating system 2 – software components, configurations 3 – software configurations data
	Attestation soundness – strength of the cryptographic proof	1 – use of mediocre cryptographic algorithms 2 – use of strong cryptographic algorithms
	Attestation freshness - Ensuring the attestation report is recent and not a replay of a previous state	1 – before deployment, replay protection 2 – frequently 3 – before each (configuration) transaction

Side-channel attack mitigation	Mitigating application fingerprinting – Alternative mechanisms can be prevented to prevent side-channels and, e.g., other processes from observing system call patterns. Effectiveness of the method depends of the adversary and platform.	0 – no mitigation 1 – system call obfuscation (e.g. wrappers) 1 – system call timing randomization 1 – constant time execution 1 – Sandboxing allowed calls 2 – Combination of mitigations
Vulnerability analysis	Known vulnerabilities vs. maturity	0 – no analysis (unmature)/ known (unpatched) vulnerabilities 1– no known vulnerabilities in mature TEE product
	Security audited and penetration tested	0 – no testing 1 – passed tests by a trusted party
Security certification	Common criteria evaluation – where assurance level indicates the depth and rigor of evaluation	0 – no certification 1 to 7 according to EAL level
	Other certification	0 – testing 1 – trusted certification

Kubernetes scheduling logic can then be built by reflecting above metrics against the operator’s requirements. As illustrated in Figure 10, the prioritization is done by selecting a) which features are mandatory and must be fulfilled with some minimal level, and b) which guide the prioritization and what are the weights for the prioritizing features. Prioritization value is the sum of weight multiplied level for required node label.

In addition to considering the confidentiality parameters, real-world implementation must also include sustainability and other quality and performance relevant parameters into prioritization decision. For instance, the time overhead and energy consumption profile values, which were measured in Section 5.2, can be directly used as levels that are included to the priority value.

Figure 10. Prioritization logic

5.4 SIDE-CHANNEL ATTACKS ON CONFIDENTIAL CONTAINERS

Figure 11. System event patterns for two containers hosting two distinct applications. Each arrow represents a system event (either a syscall or a capability), and arrows of the same colour reflect the same system event (e.g., the ‘write’ syscall or the ‘CAP_SYS_CHROOT’ capability).

5.4.1 CONTEXT

In recent work at TID, we identified a novel side-channel attack targeting confidential containers running microservices. As shown in Figure 11, containers interact with the “outside world” in two ways: (i) over the network with other containers or cloud services, and (ii) through the host OS kernel. While the first interaction is typically encrypted and has been the focus of extensive traffic analysis research (e.g., [56]), the container–kernel interface remains largely unexamined and is the focus of our investigation. Our hypothesis was that system events (e.g., system calls and capabilities) sent via the container–kernel interface can constitute a unique fingerprint of the application. Crucially, these system events can be accurately collected from outside the confidential container, without introducing overhead or being detectable. The insights gained from this fingerprinting attack could ultimately enable adversaries to conduct more effective, efficient and stealthy attacks.

5.4.2 THE ATTACK

We formulate our fingerprinting attack as a multi-class classification problem, aiming to identify which Docker image is running inside a confidential container based on the system events it triggers. The attack proceeds in two distinct phases: an offline phase, executed prior to the victim container's launch, and an online phase, carried out while the victim's confidential container is actively running.

In the offline phase, the attacker collects system events generated during the execution of various Docker images within confidential containers. The Docker images used in the offline phase may be attacker-generated, obtained from public repositories (e.g., Docker Hub), or compiled from publicly available source code. The resulting system event traces are used to train a machine learning (ML) model, where each Docker image corresponds to a distinct class. This trained classifier is then used in the online phase to perform real-time fingerprinting.

In the online phase, the attacker collects the system events generated by the victim container (this assumes co-location between the victim and the adversary, a problem that falls outside the scope for this work) and feeds them into the pre-trained model in order to infer the most likely Docker image running inside the confidential container. It is important to note that most of the computational effort is carried out during the offline phase, while the online phase serves primarily as an inference step in our evaluation.

Our attack relies on two types of system events: system calls and capabilities. For each container trace, we extract two feature types: (i) binary features indicating the presence or absence of each event, and (ii) frequency features capturing the frequency of each event. To enhance model generalization and minimize noise, we performed feature importance analysis, allowing us to discard irrelevant or low-contribution features. This process significantly reduces the dimensionality of the feature space, from 353 to 44 for system calls, and from 44 to 21 for capabilities. We then evaluated several ML models using 3-fold cross-validation combined with a grid search for hyperparameter tuning. While all models performed reasonably well, the Random Forest classifier achieved the best performance. In the following, we present detailed results, focusing on those obtained with the Random Forest classifier. For our experiments, we constructed a dataset consisting of 150 official Docker images sourced from Docker Hub.

5.4.3 RESULTS

Table 11 reports the accuracy, precision and F1-score of our trained Random Forest ML model for fingerprinting applications running within the TEE. The results are presented for Docker images executed both with and without Docker parameters, and for two feature types: binary or frequency-based vectors. The evaluation is structured in two parts: the first two rows show results using system call data, while the last two rows correspond to results based on capability data.

Table 11. Fingerprinting accuracy, precision, and F1-Score

	Random Forest (without parameters)			Random Forest (with parameters)		
	Accuracy	Precision	F1-score	Accuracy	Precision	F1-score
Binary syscall vectors	0.74	0.68	0.70	0.80	0.75	0.76
Frequency syscall vectors	0.95	0.93	0.94	0.96	0.96	0.95
Binary capability vectors	0.12	0.07	0.08	0.15	0.09	0.10
Frequency capability vectors	0.92	0.91	0.92	0.94	0.92	0.94

As shown in the first two rows of Table 11, the trained ML model achieves significantly higher accuracy, precision, and F1-score when using frequency-based feature vectors, for both system calls and capabilities. The results also suggest that fingerprinting is slightly more effective when applications are executed with their corresponding Docker parameters. Overall, these findings demonstrate that system events invoked by applications inside confidential containers can leak information, enabling adversaries to accurately infer which application is being executed.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Orchestration plays a vital role in the management of 6G networks. Its integration with the confidential computing paradigm provides cost-efficiency with security, enables new use cases, and facilitates cooperation between operators, end-users, and infrastructure providers. We have worked on the different aspects of orchestration and containerized confidentiality by exploring the major security threats, assessing feasibility and adaptability of orchestration on heterogeneous infrastructure of confidential continuum, as well as considering impacts of emerging AI technologies. This report analysed the threats and the requirements coming from the 6G use cases, discussed architectural blueprints, and documented our experiments and demonstrations for confidential orchestration.

Main observations, key takeaways, and future research recommendations:

- CoCo is a maturing project which brings confidential workflow automation easily available for various TEE-capable platforms. Our experiments highlight CoCo's feasibility also on ARM based edge devices with reasonable performance penalties. However, for many platforms CoCo is not yet available, and it remains to be seen how well the industry and open-source community are able to develop optimized solutions to support trustworthy containers in lightweight manner.
- The proposed K8s scheduling approach highlighted the need to also consider the parameters of confidential computing when orchestrating and optimizing the performance of 6G services. To support prioritization in the scheduling process we defined metrics for confidentiality. AI and data-driven orchestration will be an important part of the future networks; however, the optimization problem is not easy task. Future work is needed to develop and learn models that can capture operators' requirements for security and performance as well as run-time parameters from platforms and to transform them to automated resource allocations, prioritizations, and security configurations.
- The novel side-channel attack presented in this work demonstrates that the interactions of confidential containers with the "outside world" (which are not protected by default) can inadvertently reveal application-level information that should remain confidential. Further research is required to assess the implications of such fingerprinting attacks across a range of 6G use cases and to develop effective mitigation strategies. Particular attention should be

given to identifying which countermeasures are practical, considering the trade-offs between performance, security & privacy and deployment complexity.

- Confidential container solutions can be the backbone for secure orchestration of federated AI, integrating TEE-based model execution and DP noise injection to prevent leakage. Future work should cover designing of confidential AI pipelines that optimize trade-offs between privacy, security, and efficiency in multi-party federated learning.

This task studied the enablers for confidential orchestration. Future work is needed on studying their application for different technologies to be orchestrated and for different use cases. Within CONFIDENTIAL6G, the work continues in Task 4.4, which studies orchestration of confidential AI workloads, as well as in the use case 1 of WP5, which studies confidential orchestration in the context of an airline application scenario.

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